

Extension of Cohn's Model for Reactor Noise: Spatial Limitations and Multi-Point Perspectives

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ABSTRACT

Accurate determination of reactor kinetic parameters is a prerequisite for the safe and reliable operation of nuclear systems. Neutron noise analysis at zero power provides a non-intrusive way of extracting these parameters, and recent work by Guillevic has revisited the classical Cohn formulation, clarifying its theoretical foundation and numerical implementation. While this formulation offers a compact Lorentzian expression for the cross-power spectral density (CPSD), its applicability to realistic reactor configurations remains insufficiently assessed.

The present study extends this line of research by combining synthetic signal generation with dedicated C++ numerical tools to evaluate the predictive capabilities of this expression. A series of one-dimensional reactor models of increasing length are investigated, allowing systematic comparisons between numerical CPSDs and their theoretical counterparts. The results confirm that the model provides accurate estimates for small reactor sizes, where the point-kinetics approximation holds. However, as the system size increases, significant discrepancies emerge at high frequencies, reflecting spatial effects only partially accounted for through the spatial Diven factor.

These findings demonstrate both the strengths and the limitations of the simplified Lorentzian formulation. They underscore the need for extended models —such as multipoint kinetics— that better capture spatially dependent noise phenomena. In this respect, the present work provides a numerical benchmark that highlights where the expression remains valid and where its extension becomes necessary.

Keywords: Reactor noise, CPSD, Point-kinetics, Spatial effect

1. INTRODUCTION

The analysis of zero-power reactor noise has long been recognized as a non-intrusive and efficient method for investigating the dynamic behavior of nuclear systems under steady-state conditions. By examining correlations in detector signals, it is possible to extract key kinetic parameters such as the effective delayed neutron fraction or the prompt neutron decay constant [1, 2], which play a central role in reactor safety assessments.

Among the different theoretical models developed to interpret neutron noise, the formulation introduced by Cohn [3] has provided a compact Lorentzian expression that links the cross power spectral density (CPSD) to the point-kinetics parameters of the system. This model is used in many experimental studies but is likely to mask spatial effects [4, 5]. More recently, Guillevic [6] proposed a reformulation that improves the clarity of its theoretical basis and its connection to numerical implementations. In particular, his work relied on a dedicated C++ framework for generating synthetic detector signals and evaluating CPSDs under controlled conditions. The present PhD work is a direct continuation of Guillevic's, extending his approach to multi-region configurations in order to assess the influence of spatial effects on neutron noise observables.

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Building on this foundation, the present study focuses on assessing the validity of the point-kinetics approximation as reactor size increases. The analysis is based on the Lorentzian formulation of the Cohn model,

$$|\Phi_{ij}(f)| = P_0\delta_{i,j} + \frac{P_c}{1 + \left(\frac{2\pi f}{\alpha}\right)^2} \quad (1)$$

In this expression, P_0 represents the contribution of *uncorrelated events*, corresponding to neutrons originating from statistically independent fission chains or from unrelated external sources, and thus forming a white noise background. Conversely, P_c quantifies the power associated with *correlated events*, i.e. neutrons belonging to the same fission family or generation. The equation (4) provides a compact analytical description of the cross power spectral density (CPSD). Using the same simulation environment as Guillevic, detector signals are generated for cores of different size and their CPSDs are systematically compared to the predictions of equation (4). The objective of this work is to quantitatively evaluate the limits of the approximation by analyzing the discrepancies between the fitted parameters obtained from numerical signals and their theoretical values. It is shown that while the model yields estimates in small systems, the bias increase markedly with reactor size, indicating that spatial effects become dominant and that the point-kinetics approximation loses validity in large-core configurations.

The paper is organized as follows. First, the theoretical background and the adopted simulation framework are briefly recalled. Then, the methodology used to compare analytical and numerical CPSDs is introduced. Results are presented for different core lengths, highlighting the limitations of the point-kinetics approximation. Finally, preliminary results are proposed on a multipoint formulation of the kinetics, based on a semi-empirical expression that accounts for higher-order modes. Although this formulation is not yet complete, it demonstrates improved agreement with numerical simulations and outlines a possible direction for future theoretical refinements.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Neutron Noise Monte Carlo tool

To investigate the validity of the analytical models and to quantify the impact of spatial effects, a numerical tool capable of reproducing neutron noise under controlled conditions is required. Such a tool is necessary because analytical formulations, although insightful, rely on simplifying assumptions which can mask the influence of spatial correlations and transport effects on the noise characteristics. To overcome these limitations, a homogeneous C++ code has been developed [6], spatially discretized into a finite number of volumes. Neutron histories are initiated by external neutron sources S_{ext} and evolve in a discrete space where transfer probabilities are precomputed and stored in a fission matrix obtained from a more sophisticated Monte Carlo neutron transport code such as TRIPOLI-4[®]. This approach sets aside highly computable steps without impacting zero-power noise theory itself and the validation purpose of this paper.

The components of the fission matrix K represent the number of neutrons generated by a fission event in volume i , induced by a neutron originating from volume j . It is used as a solution to express the neutron production rate at volume i , following equation (2) in matrix form. The user may define a normalisation factor k_{imp} as a way to impose the first eigenvalue of the fission matrix. The normalisation is defined as in equation (2) where S is the neutron production rate and k_0 is the first eigenvalue of the fission matrix.

$$S = \frac{1}{k_{imp}}KS, \quad K_{imp} = \frac{k_{imp}}{k_0}K \quad (2)$$

Using the fission matrix allows the Monte Carlo tool to work as the following.

A neutron is initially emitted from an external source defined by the user. Emission occurs in a given volume, at time t_0 . The neutron is then transported to a volume i , selected according to a discrete probability $p_{i,j} = \frac{K_{imp_{i,j}}}{\bar{\nu}_i}$. If the neutron remains active, a fission event is triggered in the affected volume which emits ν new neutrons according to the probability $p_i(\nu)$. Also, the time associated with the incident neutron is incremented by a mean generation time Λ_{eff} . These secondary neutrons are then added to the list of particles to be tracked, with their own trajectories and interactions to be simulated. Each neutron from a fission event is treated independently. This process is repeated for each active neutron until a stopping criteria is met. The extinction of an individual neutron may result from leakage outside the geometric domain, absorption without fission, or exceeding the time limit imposed on the global simulation. Finally, all fission events are scored, taking into account the volume in which they occurred and the associated time. These data are used to compile the statistics needed to analyze the neutronic behavior of the studied system.

2.2. Theoretical and Numerical Methods

Once the detector time signals are obtained, the Cross Power Spectral Density (CPSD) is first evaluated numerically using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT):

$$\hat{\phi}_{i,j}^{num}[k] = \frac{1}{Ldt} (\text{FFT}\{n_i\}[k] \cdot \text{FFT}^*\{n_j\}[k]), \quad (3)$$

where L is the duration of the time series, dt the time step, and n_i, n_j the signals in volumes i and j . This evaluation will be referenced as the Monte Carlo based model.

It is then compared with an analytical reference model for the CPSD amplitude $|\Phi_{ij}(f)|$ using a regression method presented in the next section. Following the formulation proposed by Guillevic [6], itself based on earlier works [3, 7, 8, 9], the CPSD can be expressed in the simplified Lorentzian form:

$$|\Phi_{ij}(f)| = P_0 \delta_{i,j} + \frac{P_c}{1 + \left(\frac{\omega}{\alpha}\right)^2}, \quad \text{with } P_0 = \sqrt{n_i n_j}, \quad P_c = \frac{n_i n_j}{2\alpha^2 \Lambda^2 F} \left(\frac{D_\nu R_p}{1 - \rho} \right). \quad (4)$$

In this formulation, D_ν is the prompt neutron Diven factor (related to neutron multiplicity statistics), while R_p is the spatial Diven factor introduced by Otsuka and Ijima and reused by Bennet [10, 11]. The latter aims to account for spatial effects through flux-adjoint overlaps, but only partially, as it does not fully capture the complexity of spatial correlations in reactor kinetics. In this formula $\omega = 2\pi f$ is the angular frequency and F is the fission rate in the reactor. n_i, n_j are evaluated using the following: $n_i = \Phi_i * F$ with Φ_i the i -th component of the flux.

The objective of this paper is to assess the accuracy and the limits of this model (referenced as the Cohn model) when confronted with numerical simulations.

2.3. Regression Method

Parameter estimation for the Cohn model was performed by non-linear fitting of the numerical CPSD to its theoretical Lorentzian form. This approach, chosen for its flexibility in handling interdependent parameters and noisy spectral data, ensures robust adjustment across a wide frequency range. For each parameter, the mean value from independent realizations was taken as the final estimate, and the corresponding dispersion quantified its uncertainty. To evaluate robustness, relative discrepancies and standard deviations were expressed as percentages of the theoretical values, providing direct measures of predictive accuracy and fitting consistency.

$$\gamma_X = \frac{\bar{X}_{fit} - X_{theo}}{X_{theo}} = \frac{1}{X_{theo}} \left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} X_{fit}^{(k)} - X_{theo} \right), \quad \gamma_{\sigma_X} = \frac{\sigma_{X_{fit}}}{X_{theo}} = \frac{1}{X_{theo}} \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \left(X_{fit}^{(k)} - \bar{X}_{fit} \right)^2} \quad (5)$$

To avoid aliasing effects, the maximum frequency was restricted to one tenth of its theoretical value $f_{max} = \frac{1}{10 * dt}$ and the minimal frequency was defined as $f_{min} = \frac{1}{T_{simu}}$. This methodology ensures that both the central tendency and the dispersion of the fitted parameters are rigorously evaluated, while maintaining consistency with the Monte Carlo based model.

2.4. Reactor Model

The following study aims to highlight the spatial effects that occurs in a zero-power neutron noise study. To do so, we propose the following 1D reactor model :

Figure 1. General model of the 1D reactor used

This model is composed by N_v cells ($L = 1.2cm$) that contains a pellet of oxide uranium ($r = 0.4cm$) surrounded by a zircaloy clad ($R = 0.45cm$), all of witch are surrounded by water as a moderator. When the length of the reactor change, the number of cells change as well. In this work, we will study reactors of the following length : 61.2 cm, 122.4 cm, 183.6 cm, 244.8 cm and 306 cm. In any of these cases, the number of cells is different but we impose a mesh in order to fix the number of volume to 102. This means even though the reactor of length 61.2 cm have 51 cells, it has 102 volumes. The pin cell geometry and composition data are taken from a benchmark [12]. A variation of the Diven factor with reactor size was observed in [6], which we believe may result from changes in the number of mesh elements. The mesh is thus kept fine enough to prevent this effect.

For each of these reactor a TRIPOLI-4 simulation [13] is run to determine its fission matrix, then the corresponding calculation is done. At the end of this process, counting rate signals are obtained for each volumes of each reactor. The system reactivity was set to -400 pcm to ensure a slightly subcritical configuration. An external neutron source of intensity 10^6 neutrons per second was used to sustain the fluctuations. The sampling time step dt and the mean neutron generation time Λ were both fixed at $100 \mu s$, ensuring a consistent temporal resolution between simulated and theoretical signals. Each simulation covered a total duration of $T_{simu} = 200$ s, and statistical averaging was performed over 100 independent realizations to improve the accuracy and robustness of the computed spectra. The delayed neutron fraction was set to $0pcm$ to study a simpler cases first which mean the decay constant $\alpha = \frac{\beta - \rho}{\Lambda} = 40 s^{-1}$.

Based on the signals obtained with the previously described method, the temporal evolution of the count rates in a fixed volume (here : volume 51) has been plotted and compared for all the investigated reactor configurations, as shown in the Figure 2 :

Figure 2. Count rates in volume 51 for all reactor length studied

3. RESULTS

3.1. Point-Kinetic Approximation

Using these signals together with Eqs. (3) and (4), both the numerical and theoretical CPSDs can be obtained. The numerical CPSD is evaluated over 100 independent runs, and the following plot displays the individual realizations together with their average value, which is then compared to the theoretical prediction.

The Figure 3 contains CPSD for two of the reactors length (122.4cm, 306cm) when the detector 1 is considered as the left half of the reactor (from volume 1 to 51) and the detector 2 is the right half (from volume 52 to 102).

(a) Figure 3 (a): CPSD between both half of the reactor of length 122.4 cm

Figure 3 (b): CPSD between both half of the reactor of length 306 cm

A good agreement between the analytical and simulated curves can be observed in these figures; however, a slight divergence at high frequencies is noticeable in the case of the 306 cm reactor. To further investigate this behavior, the situation where the detectors are located in single volumes is analyzed in Figure 4.

Even though the analytical CPSD seems correct when a detector is considered as the half of the reactor, if each volume are observed separately, discrepancies at high frequencies become more pronounced. Especially when the length of the reactor increase due to spatial effects, illustrating the reduced validity of the point kinetic approximation.

Figure 4 (a): CPSD between volumes 51 and 90 of the reactor of length 122.4 cm

Figure 4 (b): CPSD between volumes 51 and 90 of the reactor of length 306 cm

A study is now proposed in which detector 1 is fixed in volume 51, while the position of detector 2 is varied. For each volume, the parameters of interest (P_c and α) are evaluated, and the corresponding values of γ_{P_c} and γ_α of Eq.5 are then plotted as a function of the position of detector 2 for each reactor length, see Figure 5.

Figure 5 (a): Relative bias on the correlated term P_c for detector 1 fixed in volume 51 and detector 2 placed in each position

Figure 5 (b): Relative bias on the mean neutron decay rate for detector 1 fixed in volume 51 and detector 2 placed in each position

The results discussed above indicate that while the point-kinetic approximation provides accurate estimates for small reactor cores (length < 122.4 cm), its validity rapidly deteriorates as the system size increases (from 10% for the 183.6 cm reactor up to 60% for the 306 cm reactor). Experimental studies in zero-power facilities, such as the MINERVE reactor, have also shown that spatial effects significantly influence the extraction of kinetic parameters from noise measurements [5]. This naturally raises the question of whether the assumption of retaining only the fundamental mode of the fission matrix — which is mathematically equivalent to the point-kinetic description — remains appropriate in larger configurations.

3.2. Semi Empirical Multi-Point Kinetic

To address this issue, Figure 6 shows the evolution of the fission matrix eigenvalues (left) and the associated cutoff frequencies (right) for reactors of increasing length. As the system size grows, the spectrum becomes denser and the dominance ratio $\frac{k_1}{k_0}$ decreases, indicating an enhanced contribution of higher-order spatial modes. This trend, consistently reflected in the length dependence of the cutoff frequencies, highlights the increasing role of spatial effects and the resulting limitations of the point-kinetics

approximation in extended systems.

Figure 6 (a): Evolution of each eigenvalues for different reactor length

Figure 6 (b): Evolution of each cutoff frequency for different reactor length

This observation motivates the extension of the analysis toward a multipoint kinetics framework, where all relevant eigenmodes are consistently included. Such an extension is consistent with the theoretical developments presented by Pázsit and Demazière [14]. In this context, the following equation, derived from a multipoint kinetic formulation, was considered.

$$|\Phi_{ij}(f)| = P_0 \delta_{i,j} + P_c \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{\omega}{\lambda_k}\right)^2}, \quad \text{with } P_0 = \sqrt{n_i n_j}, \quad P_c = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \frac{\mu_k^{(ij)}}{\lambda_k^2} \quad (6)$$

Where $\mu_k^{(ij)}$ corresponds to the relative contribution of each mode. A detailed derivation of these coefficients is beyond the scope of the present paper and will be presented in a future publication. The eigenvalues λ_k of the fission matrix represent the characteristic relaxation rates of the spatial neutron population modes. Although its theoretical foundation is not yet fully established and retains an empirical character, the resulting curves in Figure 7 demonstrate improved agreement with numerical simulations.

Figure 7 (a): CPSD between volumes 51 and 90 of the reactor of length 122.4 cm with the multimodal model

Figure 7 (b): CPSD between volumes 51 and 90 of the reactor of length 306 cm with the multimodal model

Regression analyses performed with this model yield, for the 306 cm reactor, $\gamma_{P_c} = 1.564 \pm 0.939\%$ and $\gamma_{\alpha} = 2.207 \pm 0.964\%$, while the simplified model gave significantly higher values of $\gamma_{P_c} = 37.752 \pm$

1.931% and $\gamma_\alpha = 18.018 \pm 1.372\%$. For a shorter reactor length of 122.4 cm, however, both models provide similar deviations (around $1\% \pm 1\%$), indicating that the influence of spatial effects is negligible in this case. This suggests that explicitly accounting for higher-order spatial modes can provide a more accurate representation of neutron noise in extended systems, and highlights the importance of revisiting simplified theoretical models.

4. CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

In this work, the Cohn method, as revisited by N. Guillevic [6], has been taken as the theoretical foundation and applied to investigate the impact of reactor core length on the validity of the point-kinetics approximation. The Monte Carlo simulations confirm that while the simplified Lorentzian expression reproduces the system behavior well for 122.4 cm or smaller cores, increasing discrepancies arise as the reactor length grows, emphasizing the role of spatial effects and the limitations of a purely pointwise description. To address these limitations, an exploratory extension based on multipoint kinetics has been introduced showing promising improvements in the agreement with Monte Carlo base signals, particularly in large-core configurations. Although this approach remains preliminary and requires further theoretical development, the results indicate that explicitly accounting for higher modes of the fission matrix can provide a more accurate representation of neutron fluctuations. Future efforts will aim at refining this multipoint formalism and consolidating its analytical basis, with the long-term objective of bridging modal theory, spatial effects, and noise analysis within a unified framework.

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